

MEDOROGA (DYSLIPIDEMIA): A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW THROUGH AYURVEDIC AND MODERN PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Dyslipidemia, a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease, is increasingly prevalent worldwide due to sedentary lifestyles and unhealthy diets. Ayurveda, the traditional Indian system of medicine, identifies lipid disorders under the term *Medoroga*, characterized by *Meda Dhatu* imbalance and *Kapha Dosha* vitiation. This review aims to correlate Ayurvedic concepts of *Medoroga* with modern understandings of dyslipidemia and assess current treatment approaches. The paper explores classical Ayurvedic texts, clinical studies, and modern medical literature to provide a comprehensive analysis.

INTRODUCTION

1. Dyslipidemia is defined as an abnormal concentration of lipids in the blood, including elevated low-density lipoprotein (LDL), total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), and/or reduced high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels. It significantly contributes to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality globally. In Ayurveda, similar clinical presentations are described under the term *Medoroga*, which refers to diseases arising from the vitiation and abnormal accumulation of *Meda Dhatu* (adipose tissue) and *Kapha Dosha*.^[1]

Ayurvedic texts like *Charaka Samhita* and *Ashtanga Hridaya* detail *Medoroga* symptoms such as obesity, lethargy, dyspnea, and excessive sweating, are associated with metabolic syndrome and lipid imbalance.^[2] With increasing recognition of lifestyle diseases, there is renewed interest in Ayurvedic formulations and therapies for metabolic disorders, including dyslipidemia.

Methods

A structured review methodology was employed. Databases including PubMed, Google Scholar, AYUSH Research Portal, and IndMED were searched using keywords: "*Medoroga*", "Ayurveda and Dyslipidemia", "*Kapha* and Lipid Disorders", "Ayurvedic formulations for cholesterol", and "Ayurvedic treatment of *Medoroga*".

Inclusion criteria

- Review articles or clinical studies published between **2010 and 2025**.
- Articles available in English
- Classical Ayurvedic literature with modern interpretation.

RESULTS

1. Conceptual Correlation: *Ayurveda* vs Modern Medicine

Ayurvedic Term	Modern Equivalent
<i>Medoroga</i>	Dyslipidemia / Metabolic syndrome
<i>Meda Dhatu Vriddhi</i>	Hyperlipidemia
<i>Kapha Dushti</i>	Obesity, Insulin resistance
<i>Ama</i>	Oxidative stress/metabolic toxins
<i>Srotorodha</i>	Atherosclerosis, vascular blockage

Medoroga originates from poor dietary habits (*Madhura, Snigdha Ahara*), sedentary lifestyle, stress, and genetic predisposition.^{[3][4]}

2. Clinical Features

- Excessive fat deposition (especially abdomen)
- Lethargy
- Breathlessness on exertion
- Excessive sweating
- Sweet cravings
- Indigestion and *Ama* symptoms.^{[5][6]}

3. Diagnosis

Ayurvedic

- *Rogi Pariksha*: Clinical examination, *Trividha Pariksha* (Darshana, Sparshana, Prashna)
- *Nidana Panchaka*: Identifying Dosha, Dushya, Agni status

Modern

- Lipid profile test: Total cholesterol, HDL, LDL, VLDL, triglycerides
- Risk stratification using CVD risk scores.^[7]

4. Ayurvedic Management

Therapy	Mechanism	Examples
<i>Shodhana</i> (Detox)	Removes <i>Ama</i> , clears <i>Srotas</i>	Virechana, Lekhana Basti ^[8]
<i>Shamana</i> (Palliative)	Corrects <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Meda</i>	Guggulu, Triphala, Trikatu ^[9]
<i>Ahara</i> (Diet)	Light, dry, bitter, spicy	Avoid milk, fried food, sweets ^[10]
<i>Vihara</i> (Lifestyle)	Exercise, walking, yoga	Avoid daytime sleep, inactivity ^[11]

Formulations like *Medohar Guggulu*, *Triphala Guggulu*, *Arogyavardhini Vati*, and *Lekhaniya Mahakashaya* have shown lipid-lowering effects.^{[12][13]}

5. Modern Biomedical Management

Statins	First-line therapy (e.g. atorvastatin, rosuvastatin)
Fibrates	TG-lowering agents
Lifestyle:	Diet, exercise, weight reduction
Monitoring	Lipid profile every 6–12 months ^{[14][15]}

6. Clinical Evidence Supporting Ayurvedic Interventions

Multiple studies report significant improvements in lipid profiles with Ayurvedic interventions:

Study	Intervention	Duration	Outcome
Kakade et al. ^[16]	<i>Yavavati</i>	45 days	↓ TC, TG, LDL; ↑ HDL
Sharma et al. ^[17]	<i>Triphala & Trikatu</i>	60 days	Improved lipid profile
Thakur et al. ^[18]	<i>Amritadya Guggulu</i>	8 weeks	Comparable to atorvastatin
Nandal et al. ^[19]	<i>Kulattha Gutika</i>	6 weeks	Improved TC, LDL, BMI
Mahawar et al. ^[20]	<i>Navaka Guggulu + Darvyadi Kwath</i>	30 days	↓ TC and body weight

DISCUSSION

The Ayurvedic concept of *Medoroga* aligns closely with the modern understanding of dyslipidemia and metabolic syndrome. The holistic approach of Ayurveda — including

personalized diet, detoxification therapies, herbal formulations, and lifestyle correction — shows significant promise in preventing and managing lipid disorders.

Studies indicate comparable efficacy of some Ayurvedic drugs to statins in mild to moderate dyslipidemia cases, with fewer side effects reported.^{[21][22]} However, standardization, dosage optimization, and mechanistic understanding of herbal interventions are still limited.

Challenges

- Lack of large-scale randomized controlled trials (RCTs)
- Variability in formulation and dosing
- Need for integration into public health guidelines

- **Future Directions**
- Conducting multicentric RCTs on Ayurvedic formulations
- Molecular-level research on active phytoconstituents
- Inclusion of Ayurveda in national programs targeting non-communicable diseases
- Development of integrative treatment model

CONCLUSION

Medoroga, as described in Ayurveda, shares key characteristics with modern dyslipidemia. Evidence suggests that Ayurvedic management, especially when integrated with modern medicine, offers effective, safe, and sustainable solutions. Further research should focus on validation through modern scientific methods and promoting Ayurveda's preventive and promotive health practices.

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